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Security and Safety of Unmanned Air Vehicles - an Overview

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Abstract: Cyber-physical systems permeate the fabric of our society, being a crucial part of what makes it possible. As such, ensuring their security is a primal concern that cannot be neglected, whether it relates to essential services, transportation or factories. But new scenarios and use cases are emerging, which require equal concern and care, as it is the case for Unmanned Air Vehicle (UAVs) technologies. Over the past years, several technological developments made it possible to create effective and inexpensive embedded computing and communications capabilities which, in their turn, were crucial for the development of modern UAVs. Such vehicles are quite diversified in terms of form and function, encompassing a wide range of implementations, from conventional drones to quad or octocopters. UAVs can be quite versatile, having found different applications, from leisure to warfare.

Even though UAVs can help achieving better performance for transportation, surveillance, agriculture and healthcare, this technology shares most of the risks and dangers of IoT devices, since UAVs, or Drones, are devices with multiple sensors that can be integrated on Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), in a similar way as an IoT device. Drones are a doorway from the digital world to interact directly in the physical world. It is predicted that as more and more UAVs are being produced, passing from thousands to millions of drones on air every day, it increases the chance of someone hacking a drone and, for example, making it collide with a rotor of an airplane. Even though drones may not have sheer firepower, their speed and mass mean they still constitute a potential danger in many scenarios, with potentially catastrophic results. Therefore, it is vital to understand the security risks and vulnerabilities associated with UAVs in order to develop mechanisms to ensure proper safety requirements, also fostering general trust and paving the way for new services and opportunities.

This paper presents an overview on the most recent developments on drone security and safety. It also presents a comparison between UAVs and IoT devices, highlighting the similarities between IoT and drone cybersecurity issues. Finally, it proposes possible solutions and countermeasures for other UAV vulnerabilities and their feasibility on the constrained field of drone ecosystems.

Keywords: Unmanned Air Vehicles, Internet of Things (IoT), Cybersecurity, Cyber Warfare.

1. Introduction

Transportation is one of the main essential services for society. Since the first industrial revolution, it has accompanied the evolution and the development of technologies, moving goods, people, merchandise and commodities for longer distances and faster speeds. Particularly, and since the first days of human flight, air transportation has been accomplished mainly by aircrafts and helicopters manned by human pilots. However, in the last two decades the use of UAVs (more commonly known as Drones) have become commonplace, firstly for military purposes and then for civil applications.

Regardless of the type of aircraft, air transportation presents specific critical security risks: an error in midair may lead to the fall of an aircraft, resulting in material or even human losses. Drones are no exception for this concern, as any security or safety issues may cause serious incidents. Still, drones can be very versatile, having many applications in the civil domain, such as reconnaissance, photography, recreational usage and transportation. According to (SESAR JU, 2016), an economic impact analysis of the entire value chain for each of the areas of demand revealed the “potential for a European market exceeding EUR 10 billion annually by 2035”. Nevertheless, turning this forecast into reality will involve studying, researching and implementing proper UAV regulations, as well as adequate security and safety solutions.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we overview the main topics related with Unmanned Aerial Vehicles, followed by a brief discussion on communication technologies for UAV environments (Section 3). Next, we analyse the similarities between UAV and IoT domains (Section 4), followed by a discussion of cybersecurity aspects and recent developments for UAV ecosystems (Section 5). Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Unmanned aerial vehicles

All UAVs are drones, but not all drones are UAVs, since the term refers to unmanned vehicles or systems, also including for instance unmanned submarines and unmanned land vehicles. This section provides an overview of the UAV ecosystem, with a specific focus on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS).

The term UAV refers to a specific type of drones, which operate on air, while the term UAS refers to the whole system inherent to the UAV. For sake of simplicity, in this paper the terms UAV and Drone will refer to the same subject. Regarding operability, an UAV can be autonomous or remotely controlled, as in the case of Remotely Piloted Aircraft Systems (RPAS).

2.1 The UAS ecosystem

The UAS landscape encompasses a diversified set of concepts, equipment, technologies and procedures, as well as its own terminology. This section overviews these aspects, providing the knowledge baseline required to fully grasp the specific characteristics of the domain. Figure 1 depicts a simplified vision of the UAS ecosystem, including the following key components:

- The Ground Control Station (GCS), typically the physical infrastructure used to remotely control and monitor the UAV Operation, facilitating all the necessary information to the human operator or system.
- The Flight Controller is the main responsible for controlling the UAV.
- Regarding communications, the term “data link” is often used to refer to the wireless links used to transport the information flow between the drone and the GCS (Yaacoub, Noura, Salman, & Chehab, 2020). Besides wireless local network technologies (e.g., Wi-Fi), commercial and military drones often resort to cellular networks (such as 4G/5G) or satellite links for UAV control and communications.

Figure 1. UAV ecosystem

2.2 Types of UAV

UAVs can be classified in three main types (Single-Rotor, Multiple-Rotor and Fixed-wing – see Figure 2), with a fourth category representing UAVs that combine more than one of them (Aircraft Compare Editorial Team, 2021).

Single-Rotor drones rely on only one main rotor to operate on air. An example of this type of drone would be a helicopter (even though it needs a second rotor to control its autorotation, it has a single the main rotor). Multi-Rotor Drones operate similarly, but rely on more than one rotor, typically four (quadcopters) or eight (octocopters). This type of drone is more common for civilian applications, being used for structure inspection, agriculture, photography and leisure, due to its maneuverability. Fixed-wing Drones may still have one or more rotors, but use fixed wings to fly, sharing the same principles of airplane aerodynamics. An example from this type of UAVs is the well-known Predator military drone (US Air Force, 2015).

Figure 2. Single-rotor drone, Quadcopter and fixed-wing Drone
(Prodrone, 2021) (DJI, 2021) (US Air Force, 2015)

UAVs come in all sizes and shapes. Their weight may vary from a few grams (DJI, 2021) to several thousands of kilograms (U.S. Air Force, 2021), with the latter category being comparable to a small airplane in terms of size, with capacity for up to 8 or 10 people. These attributes are important for regulation purposes, in order to classify different UAV types and models.

Regardless of the type of UAV, there are two operation categories related to its distance from the operator: Visual Line of Sight (VLOS) and Beyond Visual Line of Sight (BVLOS). Additionally, the term VLL (Very Low Level) refers to a certain layer of the airspace where Visual Flight Rules (VFR) flights cannot operate (except for landing and take-off) (SESAR JU, 2019). While many Drones can operate within VLOS, only the more sophisticated models can operate in BVLOS, being able to cover longer distances.

Drones are complex systems, having different parts and specialized subsystems, where all the data is gathered and then sent to the remote pilot or system. Those components make drones very similar to Internet of Things (IoT) devices. For instance, a quadcopter drone typically has a main body part, standard and pusher propellers, landing gear, flight controller, RF unit, camera and sensors (e.g., gyroscopes, barometers, accelerometers, magnetometers, rangefinders, Inertial Measurement Units). Moreover, the information provided by the sensors may be augmented by means of artificial intelligence (AI) or sensor fusion algorithms, providing capabilities such as obstacle sensing and avoidance during the execution of the flight plan – a concept known as Detect and Avoid (DAA). Fully autonomous drones are also expected to gain more prevalence in the future, once proper Air Traffic Control (ATC) coordination mechanisms and regulatory frameworks are in place.

2.3 EU regulations and flight concepts

To the best of our knowledge, available literature provides little information about UAV Flight Concepts for civil aviation, which is hardly unsurprising considering the market maturity. Despite being seemingly more mature area, there is also a lack of information regarding military UAV operations, due to their sensitive nature.

As there are many types of drones, each with different purposes, there was the necessity to organize and classify them based on the type of missions and the associated risk levels. This makes it possible to predict and plan which resources and requirements to associate with each operation. The U-Space Concept, proposed by SESAR JU (SESAR JU, 2019), addresses this issue by defining three types of Flight Concepts: *open*, *specific* and *certified*.

The *open flight concept* category is not subject to any prior operational authorization, nor to an operational declaration by the UAS operator before the operation takes place (European Commission, 2019). According to (EASA, 2019), UAS operations do not belong to the *open* category when at least one of the general criteria listed in Article 4 of the UAS Regulation is not met (e.g., the drone does not carry dangerous goods and does not drop any material). Such operations usually fall into the *specific flight concept*, which requires operational authorizations, or under the *certified flight concept*, when more strict regulation and certification are mandatory (e.g. when the operation is conducted over assemblies of people or transporting people or dangerous goods with high risk for third parties in case of accident, in which case the Drone must specifically support such scenarios (European Commission, 2019)).

3. Communication technologies for UAV environment

Communications remain a crucial factor in UAV operations, regardless of their degree of autonomy. Whether used for direct operator flight control (with or without BVLOS), to provide transponder-like capabilities or to

provide a command-and-control channel for strategic flight operations, communications play a vital role in enabling most operational scenarios, from simple 1:1 control to multi-UAV orchestration in ATC environments. This section provides a quick overview of the UAV communications landscape, from scenarios to protocols, also briefly covering the radio technologies most commonly used for such purposes.

3.1 Types of communications

As already mentioned, UAS heavily rely on different communication channels, not only to ensure control, but also to guarantee proper navigation and surveillance. The different communication scenarios in a UAS environment can be classified in four main types (Yaacoub, Noura, Salman, & Chehab, 2020):

- Drone to Drone – although not standardized, some drones come equipped with the capability of directly communicating with other drones.
- Drone to Ground Control Station – this is the most common type of communication, already standardized on several fields of application.
- Drone to Satellite – this type of communication uses GPS for controlling and monitoring the UAV from greater distances (e.g., in a BVLOS scenario). Satellite communications are deemed as reasonably secure and safe (Yaacoub, Noura, Salman, & Chehab, 2020), being heavily used in military applications, despite their high costs.
- Drone to Network – alternatively to Drone-to-Satellite communications or direct communications with the GCS, drones may communicate using cellular networks such as 5G.

3.2 Communication technologies and protocols

Communications are a vital component of the UAS environment, being critical to its operation, security and safety. To support the different communication scenarios used UAS environments, there are several types of technologies adopted. For instance, the most commonly technologies currently used for communications with the GCS are Wi-Fi (IEEE 802.11), 4G and 5G. In many cases, such communications may be public, making them prone to eavesdropping or Man-in-The-Middle (MITM) attacks. Drones may also form Mobile Ad-hoc Networks (MANETs), also called Flying Ad-hoc Networks (FANETs), possibly supported using Peer-to-Peer (P2P) technologies that may be vulnerable to Denial-Of-Service or Sybil attacks.

Furthermore, the L-band digital aeronautical communication system (LDACS), which is an upcoming air-to-ground digital communications standard for the aeronautic domain, might be leveraged for future data link applications. It operates in the L-band (around 1GHz), with excellent propagation characteristics with additional capabilities that allow it to be considered for future integrated CNS and Spectrum developments. Also, it has been demonstrated that LDACS is able to support Alternative Positioning Navigation and Timing (APNT), meaning it is a navigation backup for the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS). Furthermore, current studies are looking at how LDACS could support surveillance and RPAS command and control C2 link technologies and applications (Eurocontrol, 2021).

There is also a considerable diversity in terms of the UAS communications protocols being used for C2 and telemetry purposes. Some of those protocols were designed for generic use, such as the Message Queueing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) and the Data Distribution Service (DDS) protocols, while others were specifically designed for UAS (e.g., MAVLink). We will focus on these three examples, as they constitute a representative sample of the most popular approaches.

MQTT is a lightweight protocol that transports messages between devices, typically running over TCP/IP. It is an OASIS and ISO standard (ISO 20922 - MQTT, 2016), being designed for constrained and low-bandwidth, high-latency or unreliable IoT networks (MQTT.org, 2021). It also uses Transport Layer Security (TLS), requesting username/password and may optionally require certificates. This protocol is widely used for drone communications, for instance to control drones that transport medical samples (HiveMQ GmbH, 2021).

Figure 3 presents the publish/subscribe architecture of MQTT, including the following key components:

- The MQTT Client (subscriber and/or publisher) connects to the Broker and publishes and/or receives messages, by publishing or subscribing to specific topics, respectively.
- MQTT Broker – The Broker works as intermediary between devices, providing decoupling capabilities and ensuring that devices do not require a synchronous API to talk to each other, allowing better scalability compared to traditional client-server architectures. It persists the messages/topics published by the clients.

Figure 3. MQTT publish/subscribe architecture

DDS is a network middleware that uses a publish/subscribe pattern (DDS Foundation, 2021), allowing real-time and scalable data exchange. It is often used in ATC applications, medical devices, transportation systems and other applications that require real-time data exchange. Although similar to MQTT, it benefits from additional features, such as supporting more Quality of Service (QoS) parameters. While MQTT operates over a TCP connection (something that may pose an undesirable overhead in unstable connectivity scenarios), DDS resorts to a Real-Time Publish-Subscribe (RTPS) wire protocol for data transfer, which is transport-independent and may use UDP, TCP or other alternatives.

MAVLink is a lightweight messaging protocol for communicating with drones (Dronecode Project, Inc., 2021), following a hybrid publish/subscribe and point-to-point design pattern. The messages are defined in XML files defining the message set supported by a particular MAVLink system.

4. Similarities between UAV and IoT

Among a wide range of applications, IoT devices can be found in smart vehicles, smart buildings, health applications, energy management, environmental management, food supply, production and industry lines management (Mosenia, 2017). This latter can be particularly useful to create decentralized industries, allowing to control, monitor and manage lines from a distance. Large industries are adopting IoT to acquire real-time information about their factories, thus evolving Industrial Control Systems (ICS) and SCADA systems. These industrial systems are also known as Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT). The ease in deploying IoT devices made those devices a top choice for most of aforementioned applications, revolutionizing entire industries. However, this fast growth and scalability also brought new challenges and security risks. Due to their pervasive and ubiquitous computing, adding the internet connection and the lack of security controls, made this type of devices prone to internet-based attacks, being used for instance to create large DDoS attacks (Antonakakis, et al., 2017). This section presents a brief overview of the IoT architecture and the UAS architecture, comparing the two models and pointing out similar security challenges.

4.1 IoT reference architecture

IoT may require the connection of several different devices, which communicate with one another in a complex manner. For a better understanding of how these communication layers can be organized and studied, a simplified IoT Reference Architecture, composed of four different layers, is provided in Figure 4 and will be used in the rest of this paper.

Figure 4. IoT architecture layers

Layer 1 relates with Sensors and Actuators (e.g., a pressure sensor or a temperature sensor). This layer interfaces with the physical world, being composed of devices capable of translating physical events into data and then transforming that data into information to be used by the applications of upper layers. It can also have actuators which react to changes in the environment. This layer is also known as the perception layer.

Layer 2 relates with the Network, where the data collected from the physical layers is transferred to the upper layers – using cellular communications, Wi-fi, Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), RFID, NFC or other communication technologies. This layer also guarantees the communication between the devices from the first layer and between the components from this layer (Mosenia, 2017).

Layer 3 relates with Edge Information Technology and is also known as the Middleware Layer. It is responsible for the pre-processing and pre-analytics of the information transferred from the lower layers, which is then passed to the upper layers and systems. Since the amount of data can be very large (e.g., Big Data scenarios), without this extra layer the applications could be flooded with data, endangering their efficiency and performance. The processing of data is thus initiated on this layer (Mosenia, 2017).

Layer 4 relates with the usage of Cloud Analytics and Data Centres. The previously pre-processed information is processed in this last layer and presented to the users and the main applications for analysis. It is also known as the Application Layer or the Business Layer.

4.2 IoT security challenges

The attacks against IoT, presented in Table 1, can be analysed from four perspectives, according to (Francesca Meneghello, 2019).

Type of Attack	Description
Ignoring Functionality	In this type of attacks, the functionalities of the device are ignored, and only the capability to connect the device to the internet or to other nodes is exploited. This opens a door to the system and allows the attacker, for instance, to create botnets.
Reducing Functionality	By controlling and reducing the functionality of a device, the attacker can ask for ransom or reduce the effectiveness of the whole system, causing malfunctions, loss of data and functionality, or even permanent damage to physical resources.
Misusing Functionality	After exploiting a device, the attacker can use it for purposes other than those the device was originally designed for. For instance, an attacker can exploit a heat system or a sound system and cause discomfort to the users by turning up the heat or by playing annoying sounds.
Extending Functionality	In this type of attacks, for instance, an IP camera can be hacked to be used against the owners of a house, by controlling the camera and watching them without permission.

Table 1. Functionality of attacks against IoT

Next, the potential weaknesses of each layer are discussed. The devices from Layer 1 are deployed in the physical environment, which makes them prone to physical attacks. Moreover, especially when using wireless technologies, their communications are also prone to interception by malicious agents. Further, those devices have limited computation capabilities and limited battery power, making them more prone to cyberattacks. For

instance, a malicious agent can add another node to the system, sending Malicious Data, causing a DoS attack by depriving other nodes from sleep mode and thus preventing them from saving energy (Shivangi Vashi, 2017). Hardware Trojans are possible to succeed in unsupervised nodes by inserting or substituting parts of the hardware of the devices. Also, side-channel attacks are possible, by analysing the power consumptions and other information about the device's lifecycle. Other issues faced by this layer are mainly related with authentication, confidentiality and access control.

Layer 2 is composed of routers, access points and other wireless or wired devices, facing even more threats than traditional information systems networks, due to the openness characteristics of IoT, with lack of strong security mechanisms and weak protocols. Known attacks associated with this layer include Sybil Attacks, Sinkhole Attacks, Sleep Deprivation Attacks, DoS attacks, Malicious code Injection, MiTM attacks, routing attacks and injection of fraudulent packets.

Layers 3 and 4 represent the higher-level components of the architecture. They are prone to some of the problems faced by common information systems. Some of the security issues faced by these layers are malware, DoS attacks, Phishing, Spear-Phishing and sniffing attacks.

To prevent and mitigate these attacks, it is important to know which characteristics are relevant to guarantee adequate security. Besides the fundamental Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability properties (commonly known as the C-I-A Triad) there are other, often overlooked aspects, that may be also important, such as accountability and non-repudiation. Ultimately, the priority and importance of certain characteristics may depend on the specific nature of each device or use case. For instance, while in a wireless implanted medical device, integrity and availability take priority over confidentiality, in industrial systems it is more important to guarantee availability prior to confidentiality. Nevertheless, and regardless of the fact that security priorities may change according to specific use cases, markets or industries, implementation of proper defence-in-depth strategies may ultimately require paying attention to all the relevant aspects.

4.3 Comparison between UAVs and IoT

UAVs typically include a number of sensors, interconnected or connected to a central unit, that use a transmitter/receiver to communicate with the GCS or the flight controller. Those sensors are relatively close to one another, compartmentalized in the same space. In comparison, traditional IoT environments are much more open and may be much larger (see Figure 5), up to thousands of devices, and adding/removing devices is a less rigid process. Those devices can be interconnected to one another or communicate through routers or gateways. This way, while in traditional IoT it is easy to add or subtract a device, in UAVs the manufacturer designed and developed the aircraft based on a fixed (or at least very restricted) number of sensors.

Figure 5. IoT architecture and sensors disposition

Figure 6 proposes a UAV architecture reference model. This reference model can be directly compared with the IoT reference architecture provided in Figure 6, in order to better highlight the similarities between these two domains. This UAV reference model also features four different layers. Layer 1 corresponds to UAV Sensors and Actuators, i.e., the physical layer where the UAV sensors will react to physical events, capturing data and transmitting that data to the actuators and/or to the upper layers of the architecture. Layer 2 corresponds to the Network and Data Link. This layer represents the communications and the data link between the UAV and the GCS. Layer 3 corresponds to the Ground Control Station, being responsible for acquiring and presenting the data sent by the UAV to the Drone Operator, as well as for sending commands to the UAV. Finally, Layer 4 corresponds to Cloud Analytics and Data Centres, being therefore related to the Business layer.

Figure 6. UAV architecture reference model

Despite the apparent similarities between the IoT and UAV reference models, they often differ when it comes to integration. IoT architectures usually encompass a diversified array of communications and control requirements, which are usually linked to the specific nature of a process or use case scenario. Thus, while some IoT systems may require real-time deterministic communications and control, others may be perfectly suited to rely on asynchronous communication mechanisms, supported by delay-tolerant networks or scenarios with unstable connectivity. For UAVs (which often incorporate a diversified array of sensor and actuator components, both for operational and mission-related purposes – see Figure 7), tracking and control requirements are not as strict as in typical hard-real time process loops, but there still are certain safety thresholds that must be ensured for reliable synchronous control – this is partially true even for (semi)autonomous UAVs, which have specific requirements for mission control and tracking purposes.

Figure 7. UAV architecture and sensor disposition

5. Cybersecurity and Safety for UAV ecosystems

Drones have offered new ways of transport, surveillance and monitoring, being used in several areas and due to their versatility, both for military and civilian applications. However, those systems might present a set of vulnerabilities and threats, some of them shared with IoT devices, that need to be addressed. Regarding UAV Security and Safety, it's vital to ensure that the communication channels provide confidentiality, integrity, availability, authentication and non-repudiation properties (Yaacoub, Noura, Salman, & Chehab, 2020), although for communications the most valuable and prioritized characteristic is integrity, ensuring proper communication

between air (UAV) and ground (ATC, UAV operator). Such requirements depend on a set of crucial capabilities, namely:

- Authorization, allowing to assign privileges to personnel in the UAS context and implement Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) mechanisms.
- Authentication, providing multi-factor authentication, mutual authentication mechanisms (especially relevant for Machine-to-Machine communications), use of Perfect Forward Secrecy (PFS) and robust encryption techniques.
- Auditing/Accounting, implementing proper mechanisms for log collection, aggregation and storage, supporting auditing procedures for post-mortem incident analysis or identification of non-conform procedures.

Regarding UAV Cybersecurity, Table 2 presents the most common cyber-attacks against drones and the correspondent security countermeasures that can be implemented.

Drone Cyber-Attacks	Security Measure
Malware	Hybrid lightweight IDS, Control access, system integrity solutions and multi-factor authentication
Backdoor Access	Hybrid lightweight IDS, Vulnerability assessment, Multi-factor robust authentication scheme
Injection/modification	Machine-Learning hybrid IDS, Time stamps, Message authentication or Digital signature
Fabrication	Assigning privilege, Multi-factor authentication, Message authentication or Digital signature
Scanning	Hybrid lightweight IDS or Honeypot, Encrypted traffic/stream
Eavesdropping	Securing communication/traffic, secure connection
Man-in-the-Middle	Lightweight hybrid IDS, Multi-factor authentication & lightweight strong cryptographic authentication protocol
Skyjet	Lightweight IDS at the physical layer, Strong & periodic passwords, strong encryption algorithm, Security Awareness
Wi-fi Jamming	Redundancy, Frequency hopping, frequency range variation
De-authentication	Lightweight IDS, Security Awareness, Frequency hopping, frequency range variation
Replay	Frequency hopping, time stamps
Buffer overflow	Lightweight IDS, proper validation
ARP Cache Poison	Lightweight IDS, Encryption
Denial of Service	Redundancy
GPS Spoofing	Return-to-base, frequency range variation

Table 2. UAV cyberattacks and security measures

Next, we provide a brief discussion of the most common attacks identified in Table 2:

- Injection/Modification – in this attack malicious or modified data is injected, leading to malfunctions on the drone or infections with malicious content.
- Fabrication - this attack aims at disrupting authenticity by trying to gain privileges to inject data or to access drone components.
- Skyjet – this is another Wi-Fi attack, presented by (He, Chan, & Guizani, 2017), in which an attacker searches for drones in the vicinity, takes control of those drones, turning them into zombie drones, and uses then the aircrack-ng tool to deauthenticate the drone and assume control over it.
- Wi-fi jamming – this type of attack jams all the wireless communications within a specified coverage area. Although this attack has some limitations, it can be catastrophic if succeeded during a long period of time, since UAS control may rely on this technology.
- Replay – a DoS attack in which data is intercepted and delayed or retransmitted at a later stage.
- Buffer Overflow – a DoS attack in which the network is flooded with requests to disrupt the drone connection.
- ARP Cache Poison – a Man-in-the-Middle attack which exploits the Address Resolution Protocol (ARP) messages, associating the attackers’ MAC Address to the target IP address, therefore allowing him to intercept the victim’s traffic (The MITRE Corporation, 2021). This technique can also be used to disconnect the Drone from the controller and/or the GCS.
- GPS Spoofing – probably one of the most known attacks against drones, GPS Spoofing refers to the type of attack which tries to give false GPS signals to the Drone receivers. This can cause malfunctions and

even control over the UAS, for instance, as it may be headed to an unwanted place instead of the base station. Since civilian GPS systems are typically not encrypted, due to cost and strategy reasons, it is very difficult to counter this type of attacks (Yaacoub, Noura, Salman, & Chehab, 2020).

Besides the UAS ecosystem cyberthreats that may be exposed by certain exploitable vectors, there are other relevant issues to be accounted for, namely: technical, operational and natural issues. The first are a direct consequence of the complex nature of UAS as systems of systems, composed of many electronic components prone to fail, such as batteries, propellers, software and even communications. Operational issues may arise as a consequence of lack of operator skills or deficient flight planning, putting the UAS in danger with potential risks of collateral damage. Finally, natural issues such as wind and rain also constitute a serious threat for UAS operation, as they may push components beyond their acceptable operation thresholds in terms of environmental parameters and mechanical stress.

Communications, Navigation and Surveillance (CNS) constitute the three fundamental pillars on top of which operational drone safety is built upon. Navigation helps leading the aircraft to the intended destination(s). Surveillance refers to monitoring its operating status and location (by simple visual contact or through more sophisticated techniques, such as GPS or radar). Communications guarantee that information is passed back and forth through the right channels and between the involved parts – a vital component of UAS security and safety. The main difference between manned and unmanned aviation is the physical location of the human controller: while on the former the pilot is onboard, on UAS the controller is located on a remote pilot station. This imposes new risks to be considered, during both the pre-flight and the in-flight phases, to protect these three fundamental services. Any successful attack during any of these phases may lead to catastrophic results, but threats may not present the same risk level for both phases. For instance, GPS jamming has more impact during in-flight, whereas in pre-flight (while the drone is on the ground) it represents a less serious threat.

To better understand this, it is important to note which services or procedures correspond to each flight phase.

The *pre-flight phase* comprises the pilot training, strategic conflict resolution, communication with the ATC, weather information, traffic information, drone maintenance and inspection. During this phase, some services can be targeted for cybersecurity attacks, for instance to acquire information about the drone mission, to compromise some of the components that may be critical during the flight phase, or even to provoke a Denial-of-Service situation. To achieve this, attackers may recur to well-known information systems threats, such as malware, backdoors, virus, trojans, MiTM, DoS and ARP cache poison. To help mitigate these risks, Ground Control Stations, UAS Operators and U-Space Service Providers (USSP) can rely on known existing standards and guidelines, such as the NIST Cybersecurity Framework for Critical Infrastructures (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2018) or ISO 27002 (ISO 27002, 2013), to mention a few.

During the *in-flight phase* the UAV may need to communicate with the ATC, the Ground Control Station and the Flight Controller. This phase also encompasses weather information, traffic information, CNS monitoring and tactical conflict resolution. During in-flight, attackers may focus on more mission-critical components, such as the CNS infrastructure, the ATC communication or the drone communications. In this type of scenario, attackers may use techniques such as injection/modification, fabrication, scanning, eavesdropping, MiTM, skyjet, wi-fi jamming, replay, buffer overflow, ARP Cache Poison, DoS and GPS Spoofing.

To help addressing this variety of threats, threat-trees like those proposed by (Almulhem, 2020) can be very beneficial for designing cybersecurity mechanisms. This approach helps modeling and representing threats in a tree-shape diagram to a particular system and from a high-level perspective. Although it does not ensure complete representation of all possible threats, it offers an initial point of start. It is important to mention that the threat-tree may differ for different systems architectures, even within the UAS domain. To further analyze possible threats in a system and ones that might have not been addressed using the previous technique, simulated environments (Mairaja, Babab, & Javaid, 2019) may help researching for vulnerabilities and security issues in drones and communication protocols, as well to better understand UAV technologies, reducing experimentations time and costs.

The specific nature of the UAS cybersecurity domain, as well as its intersection with the particularly strict requirements of the aeronautical industry, can only be adequately tackled by means of a significant investment in two crucial areas.

The first area is Regulation and Standardization. Contrary to the IoT industry, the aviation industry is a well-regulated and standardized sector, benefiting from synergies derived from common efforts and oriented goals. Since the early 2000's, Eurocontrol and other aviation entities, like the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), are regulating, publishing standards and guidelines for the UAS industry, that help protecting the different stakeholders. Additionally, this industry benefits from adopting standards from related areas, such as the NIST Cybersecurity framework or the ISO 27002, serving as guidelines for the implementation of Security and Information Management systems.

The second area is Research & Development. As part of a unified industry approach, there is a considerable effort, both in the EU and internationally, to research, develop and deploy a standardized Air Traffic Management (ATM) infrastructure. This effort has spawned several developments, such as the U-Space Traffic Management initiative (UTM) (SESAR JU, 2019). An example of this common effort is the development of a common Public Key Infrastructure framework for the System Wide Information Management (SWIM), led by Eurocontrol and involving a large number of industry partners. This framework is planned to be deployed until the end of 2021, ensuring interoperability of digital certificates within Europe and other regions and offering security and encryption for the communications (Eurocontrol, 2021).

Overall, these developments show to which extent the industry is committed towards the development of proper regulations and support infrastructure, which are deemed vital for the mass introduction of UAV-supported services expected to have a disruptive effect in many different sectors, such as healthcare, delivery of goods and surveillance or emergency relief support.

6. Conclusion and future work

This paper presented the main topics related to UAS security, considering the whole UAV ecosystem and regulations, and pointing out different communication technologies and protocols relevant for the security of UAS communications. The similarities between UAV and IoT were explored in order to provide a different perspective of UAV cybersecurity, including the highlighting of several attacks and corresponding countermeasures and the discussion of recent developments in the aviation industry.

The implementation of standards and the application of risk and cybersecurity frameworks are important and should be used to make the UAV ecosystems more resilient to cybersecurity attacks. Furthermore, research of new vulnerabilities and the development of new architectures for UAV ecosystems, using simulated environments, plays a key role to deploy faster and better solutions.

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